

Toward 1.5°C household footprints: scenarios of lifestyle change adoption in Europe under industrial decarbonization

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Abstract

Lifestyle changes can play a crucial role in aligning household carbon footprints with the Paris Agreement's 1.5°C target. However, the adoption levels required of these changes may vary even among similar countries. Additionally, the combined effects of socioeconomic and technological changes on lifestyle-based mitigation potential remain underexplored. Here, we estimate the population-wide adoption levels at which three lifestyle change portfolios of 47 individual consumption changes reach 1.5°C-compatible footprint targets for five European Union countries (Germany, Spain, Hungary, Latvia, and Sweden) in 2030 and 2050, evaluated within an EXIOBASE-based scenario model reflecting 1.5°C-compatible industrial decarbonization. We assessed per-capita carbon footprints under lifestyle change adoption scenarios in comparison to 1.5°C-compatible targets, estimated potential financial savings, and evaluated the effects of various rebound re-spending patterns. Our scenario analysis indicates that while all five countries have a theoretical pathway to 1.5°C-compatible household carbon footprints in 2030, high adoption levels of high-impact lifestyle changes were required, especially for countries with higher initial footprints. In 2050, the 1.5°C target was reached in only two of five countries through (nearly) universal high-impact lifestyle change adoption across the population combined with a decarbonized background system. Directing re-spending from the average lifestyle change consumption pattern toward low-emission categories yielded less benefit than avoiding high-emission rebounds in our scenario analysis. Overall, our results show how achieving 1.5°C-compatible lifestyles in high-income countries would require a comprehensive transformation of both individual consumption patterns and systemic structures, which we discuss may not be feasible in practice with existing socioeconomic constraints.

Keywords: Lifestyle change, Multiregional Input-Output (MRIO) analysis, carbon footprints, sufficiency, climate target, rebound effects

1. Introduction

There is a critical need to limit global warming to 1.5°C to avoid severe climate-related effects, such as extreme weather events, biodiversity loss, and socioeconomic instability (Armstrong McKay et al., 2022; Hoegh-Guldberg et al., 2019; Ripple et al., 2024; Warren et al., 2022; Wunderling et al., 2023). Achieving this target requires profound emissions reductions across all economic sectors, with net-zero CO₂ reached by mid-century (Rogelj et al., 2018). Integrated Assessment Model (IAM)-based mitigation scenarios dominate the policy landscape but primarily focus on supply-side measures and carbon dioxide removal, giving limited consideration to demand-side measures (Mundaca et al., 2019). Supply-side changes alone are unlikely to deliver emissions reductions consistent with 1.5°C (Bjørn et al., 2018; Cap et al., 2024; de Koning et al., 2016), particularly without large-scale carbon dioxide removal (van Vuuren et al., 2018; Warszawski et al., 2021).

Lifestyle changes are a critical demand-side complement to technological decarbonization, and their importance will grow as energy and other industrial systems decarbonize (Bjelle et al., 2021). The IPCC estimates that demand-side actions across agriculture, buildings, and transport domains could reduce global emissions by 40-70% by 2050 (Creutzig et al., 2022). These estimates are informed by analysis from tools such as life cycle assessment (LCA) and input-output analysis (IOA), which are capable of modeling the effects of detailed demand-side changes (Ivanova et al., 2020). However, studies assessing the carbon footprint reduction potential of demand-side actions (Guan et al., 2025; Moran et al., 2020; Vita et al., 2019) have not yet accounted for the effects of industrial decarbonization. Previous research has explored global- or regional-level scenarios towards 2°C (de Koning et al., 2016; Girod et al., 2014) or single-country scenarios analyzing the contribution of industry and lifestyle change (Bjørn et al., 2018; Morfeldt et al., 2023), but none examine the combination of lifestyle change and industrial decarbonization aligned with a 1.5°C pathway across multiple countries. Modeling varied portfolios of consumption changes within a 1.5°C-compatible industrial mitigation scenario can quantify the scale of lifestyle change required beyond what technological decarbonization can deliver, which has a particular urgency in high-income regions with the strongest need for action.

The European Union (EU) represents a strong case study for demand-side mitigation research. Equity-based interpretations of the 1.5°C ambition argue that regions with higher incomes and per-capita emissions have a responsibility to reduce emissions faster and earlier (Fanning & Hickel, 2023; Hickel, 2020; Rogelj et al., 2018). The EU has among the highest per-capita emissions and incomes (Ivanova et al., 2016) and relies heavily on foreign resources to support its consumption levels (Tukker et al., 2016). The region also has an explicit commitment to 1.5°C through the European Green Deal (European Commission, 2021), making it one of the few regions where high consumption levels and ambitious policy ambition converge. A multi-country analysis within the EU can reveal how differences in consumption structure or decarbonization trajectories may influence demand-side mitigation, just as factors such as the energy mix and socio-economic or geographical drivers affect carbon footprints (Ivanova et al., 2017).

The main aim of this study is to explore how lifestyle changes could contribute to reducing household carbon footprints to 1.5°C-compatible levels in a selection of EU countries in 2030 and 2050. We estimate the average population-wide adoption level of three lifestyle change portfolios of 47 individual consumption changes compatible with a 1.5°C target. Lifestyle change portfolios are evaluated with an input-output scenario model incorporating 1.5°C-aligned industrial decarbonization, isolating the additional mitigation potential of lifestyle change beyond what technological change alone can deliver. Rebound effects from financial savings and the effect on adoption levels are also assessed.

2. Methods

2.1. Calculating carbon footprints with input-output analysis

Consumption-based accounting measures the total inputs embodied in the goods and services consumed by end users, such as households (Leontief, 1970; Miller & Blair, 2009). In environmentally extended input-output analysis (EE-IOA), the movement of goods and services through the global economy is integrated with national environmental accounts to connect local production impacts with global consumption patterns (Miller & Blair, 2009). Multi-regional input-output (MRIO) tables provide a consistent framework for representing the effects of the adoption of new consumption patterns of technologies (Wiebe et al., 2018; Wood et al., 2018). This approach enables the efficient calculation of the global direct and indirect effects of changes in household consumption. A household carbon footprint can then be calculated via EE-IOA for various household consumption patterns.

The lifestyle change portfolios were applied to a partially decarbonized MRIO scenario model developed in prior work (Cap et al., 2024) from EXIOBASE 3.8.2 (Stadler et al., 2021; Stadler et al., 2018). All major greenhouse gases reported in EXIOBASE (CO₂, CH₄, N₂O, SF₆, HFCs, and PFCs) were considered in carbon footprint calculations. The GHG emissions were converted to CO₂-equivalent values (CO₂e) by IPCC AR6 global warming potentials with a 100-year time horizon (IPCC, 2022).

The partially decarbonized scenario model translated parameters from the IMAGE interpretation of SSP1-RCP1.9, a sustainability-focused development pathway in line with a 1.5°C trajectory, into EXIOBASE from a baseline year of 2015 (Cap et al., 2024). This scenario model incorporates industrial decarbonization across energy, transport, agriculture, and buildings along with socioeconomic developments including population change, productivity-driven economic growth, and changes to household consumption patterns from greater income. These socioeconomic and technological transitions are referred to here as background system changes.

The scenario model is considered partially decarbonized because technology-focused consumption changes at the household level, which are embedded in sectoral decarbonization pathways for transportation and building sectors, are not included as a background change. Although policies and economic incentives may encourage household-level technology uptake, actual adoption can involve lifestyle changes depending on incurred costs or available infrastructure (van den Berg et al., 2019).

2.2. Constructing lifestyle change portfolios

We selected Germany (DE), Spain (ES), Hungary (HU), Latvia (LV), and Sweden (SE) as case study countries to capture diversity across the EU based on factors that drive differences in carbon footprints (Ivanova et al., 2017): income and consumption levels, household size, heating demand, transportation demand, dietary patterns, and carbon intensity of the electricity mix (see Cap et al. (2025) for further elaboration on country selection). These countries were also selected for access to data on consumer preferences obtained through citizen thinking labs (Vadovics et al., 2024), which allowed for a lifestyle change portfolio incorporating consumer preferences between domains to be analyzed.

We defined lifestyle change portfolios as combinations of consumption changes adopted by a share of the population, spanning the domains of mobility, housing, nutrition, and other (Figure 1). The 47 consumption change options were defined through a literature review and expert analysis (Vadovics et al., 2024) and parametrized in an MRIO scenario model for the five countries for 2015, 2030, and 2050 (Cap et al., 2025). Each option was modeled as the full theoretical uptake by an eligible share of the population, accounting for thresholds such as minimum floor space, households eligible for rooftop solar, and job compatibility with home office (Cap et al., 2025).

This allowed the overall portfolio adoption level to represent the extent to which a portfolio of lifestyle changes would be adopted by the (eligible) population. Some of the consumption change options were compatible with others within a domain, while others were not. All consumption change options were divided into groups with all other mutually exclusive options (Figure 1). Because some of the

consumption changes were grouped with mutually exclusive options, the adoption level of the individual options could be lower than the level of the overall portfolio. The adoption level a_i of individual option i is determined by the overall portfolio adoption level A and an adjustment factor, which is the reciprocal of the number of mutually exclusive options in the group to which option i belongs (g_i) (Eq. 1):

$$a_i = A \cdot \frac{1}{g_i}, \text{ where } 0.01 \leq A \leq 1 \text{ and } g_i \geq 1 \quad (1)$$

We defined three portfolios: *General*, *General with preferences*, and *Highest impact* (Figure 1). *General* involved a (partial) adoption of all consumption change options, where all 47 options were included in the portfolios in all scenario years to ensure comparability. *General with preferences* included the same options, with adjusted adoption levels following domain-level preference weights. Preference weights derived from Vadovics et al. (2024) are Nutrition: 1.0; Mobility: 0.85; Housing: 1.05; Leisure/Other: 1.05. As all adoption levels were capped at 100%, the *General with preferences* portfolio only meaningfully diverges from *General* at lower overall adoption levels where differences across domains are more apparent. The *Highest impact* portfolio selected the option(s) with the greatest carbon footprint reduction potential within each mutually exclusive group (based on 2030 values from Cap et al. (2025); see Figure 1 for groups), offering the best chance at reaching the 1.5°C target. In the case of multiple similarly high-impact options in a group, the adoption level was divided proportionally among the high-impact options.

When consumption change options are combined into portfolios, their impacts depend on the structure of the MRIO model, which is progressively altered by the inclusion of prior options. Consequently, the effectiveness of an option can increase or decrease depending on the presence of complementary measures, such as the availability of renewable electricity for an electric vehicle or living space reduction in combination with a heat pump. To address these interactions, consumption change options were ordered and assessed to determine whether their modeling should be applied to the baseline model structure or the already adjusted model structure (Table S1).

When modeling a lifestyle change portfolio, the model was adjusted sequentially from the baseline model (v_0), with each iteration (v_i) created by applying a consumption change. The model was adjusted for each consumption change from one of two methods, based on whether the consumption change modeling for that option should account for the existing adjusted model structure (“Default model” type) or the baseline model structure (“Baseline reference” type), see Table S1. When accounting for the existing adjusted model structure, the model was updated by multiplying the previous iteration (v_{i-1}), which already incorporates prior consumption changes, by a set of scalars representing a new consumption change, producing the next iteration (v_i). When accounting for the baseline model structure, the set of scalars was used to calculate a deviation from the baseline model, which was then subtracted from the previous iteration (v_{i-1}) to generate the new iteration (v_i).

Figure 1. Consumption change options categorized into domains and mutually exclusive groups in the General and Highest impact lifestyle change portfolios. The same Group number (G-) indicates that options belong to the same group. The bar length represents the adjustment factor for options, which is the inverse of the group size for the General portfolio and the inverse of the selected options in a group for the Highest impact portfolio.

2.3. Rebound effects from financial savings

Lifestyle change portfolios were assessed with and without rebound re-spending effects. The financial effects of individual consumption change options adopted in isolation were obtained from Cap et al. (2025). These option-level effects were aggregated to calculate the overall change in household final demand expenditure resulting from the adoption of each lifestyle change portfolio.

As a default, average rebound effects from lifestyle change scenarios were approximated by proportionally redistributing any financial savings across the final demand structure of each portfolio, following rebound estimations of other IOA-based studies (Moran et al., 2020; Vita et al., 2019). This default assumption reflects the average emission intensity of the final demand structure associated with each lifestyle change portfolio in 2030 or 2050.

To estimate the possible range of rebound effects across different behavioral assumptions, we also analyzed the effects of directing rebound re-spending exclusively toward product categories with either low or high emissions intensities. Product categories with the lowest and highest emissions intensities in 2030 were selected from Cap et al. (2024), ensuring categories were present across all five countries and reflected realistic household expenditure (e.g., excluding further energy or food consumption). *Education* and *Recreation/culture/sports* were selected as low-impact categories and *Air travel* and *Cruises/ferries* represented high-impact categories. Emissions intensities for these categories in 2030

and 2050 reflected the 1.5°C-aligned industrial decarbonization trajectories of the corresponding industries.

2.4. Final demand reduction as an additional mitigation measure

For countries overshooting the 1.5°C-compatible target after implementation of the *Highest impact* lifestyle change scenario, a further emissions reduction approach was explored. To assess the theoretical magnitude of consumption reductions compatible with a 1.5°C target in these cases, we modeled an overall reduction in household final demand. Household final demand in the *Highest impact* portfolio was reduced by increments of 1% while keeping food product demand constant until the carbon footprint was below the 1.5°C target. Household direct emissions were scaled proportionally to the changes to household final demand of energy carriers using price conversions based on EXIOBASE supply-use tables (Stadler et al., 2018) and IPCC emission factors (IPCC, 2021), following the approach described in Cap et al. (2024).

2.5. Household carbon footprints and target

To assess the effect of the lifestyle change portfolios, the total household footprint was calculated from the MRIO model adjusted for lifestyle changes. We calculated the total household carbon footprint e_{hh} as the dot product of the direct intensity matrix of emissions coefficients S ; household final demand vector y_{hh} , combined with the vector of direct household emissions $s_{y_{hh}}$, which is separately derived based on specific household activities (Eq. 2).

$$e_{hh} = (S \cdot L \cdot y_{hh}) + (s_{y_{hh}}) \quad (2)$$

Where L is equal to $(I - A)^{-1}$, with matrix A made of inter-industry input-output coefficients and identity matrix I .

The resulting footprint was compared against household carbon footprint targets: 2.38 tCO_{2e} per capita in 2030 and 0.61 tCO_{2e} per capita in 2050. These targets were calculated from median emissions in 2030 and 2050 in 1.5°C-compatible pathways from the IPCC AR6, accounting for population projections and share of household emissions, as described in Cap et al. (2024). For context, we present the emissions overshoots against the 1.5°C targets after industrial decarbonization from Cap et al. (2024) in Tables S2-S3.

3. Results

3.1. Theoretical adoption levels for meeting the 1.5°C targets in 2030 and 2050

In a partially decarbonized scenario, meeting the 2030 1.5°C target of 2.38 tCO_{2e} per capita required additional household carbon footprint reductions from lifestyle change ranging from 26% (Latvia) to 50% (Germany) (Table S2). All five countries had at least one scenario where this was achievable (Figure 2). The maximum reduction achievable through lifestyle change in 2030, defined here as maximum uptake of the *Highest impact* portfolio without rebound effects, ranged from 45% (Latvia) to 71% (Hungary).

Spain and Hungary could meet the 2030 target in all three lifestyle change portfolio scenarios, including when accounting for general rebound re-spending. In Germany, Latvia, and Sweden, only the *Highest impact* portfolio scenario was compatible with the target when rebound effects were included. The *General* portfolio scenario was compatible with the 1.5°C target in Germany and Latvia when rebound effects were excluded, but a 6% overshoot occurred in both countries with full adoption and general rebound re-spending. In Sweden, full adoption of the *General* portfolio exceeded the 1.5°C target by 0.5 tCO_{2e} per capita before accounting for rebound effects, but rebound re-spending increased this overshoot to 0.69 tCO_{2e} per capita.

In 2050, emissions reductions compatible with the 1.5°C target were achieved in fewer countries and under fewer lifestyle change scenarios (Figure 2). Full adoption of the *Highest impact* portfolio could

reduce household carbon footprints by 1.1-2.7 tCO₂e (51-81%) relative to the partially decarbonized 2050 baseline, but this was insufficient to reach the 0.61 tCO₂e per-capita target in most cases. Spain and Hungary had the lowest resulting footprints with full adoption under the *Highest impact* portfolio scenario, but footprints exceeded the 1.5°C-compatible level when including rebound re-spending. Germany, Latvia, and Sweden overshot the target before accounting for any rebound emissions from re-spending by 0.38, 0.47, and 0.81 tCO₂e per capita, respectively. Under the *General* lifestyle change scenario, no country achieved 1.5°C-compatible reductions even with full portfolio adoption.

For comparison with the combined industrial and lifestyle change impact, we calculated the carbon footprints of lifestyle change implemented without background system change, reflecting the effect of lifestyle change taken in the 2015 baseline year (Figure S1). Lifestyle change applied without background change was insufficient for 1.5°C-compatible emissions reductions in all scenarios but one: full adoption of the *Highest impact* portfolio with rebound effects suppressed in Hungary in 2030 (Figure S1). Overall, background decarbonization and lifestyle changes had a negative synergy, with combined industrial decarbonization and lifestyle change mitigation potential estimates in 2050 resulting in 2-23% lower decarbonization effects than purely additive estimates (Table S5).

3.2. Financial effects

All lifestyle change portfolio scenarios generated some degree of financial savings, reflected in reduced final demand, across countries and years (Figure 3). In 2030, the *Highest impact* portfolio produced slightly lower financial savings than the *General* lifestyle change portfolio. By 2050, this pattern weakened or reversed in most countries, with greater savings under the *Highest impact* portfolio scenario in Spain and Latvia and similar financial savings in Germany and Hungary. Between 2030 and 2050, financial savings increased for all portfolios in Spain, Hungary, and Latvia. In contrast, financial savings decreased slightly in Sweden across the two scenario years, and in Germany, the financial savings from the *General* portfolio slightly decreased while the *Highest impact* portfolio increased.

Financial savings varied substantially between countries. Sweden and Germany showed lower relative financial savings than other countries, but their higher levels of household final demand meant that the absolute potential for rebound re-spending was comparable or even larger. In contrast, Latvia and Hungary showed the largest relative savings in 2050 (25% and 21% of household final demand, respectively), yet their absolute savings remained smaller due to the lower baseline consumption levels. Spain was associated with the largest absolute financial savings in 2050 in the *Highest impact* scenario (19% of household final demand), while Sweden showed the smallest relative change (4%).

3.3. Adoption levels across lifestyle change scenarios

Achieving emission reductions consistent with the 1.5°C target in 2030 required high adoption levels in the scenarios analyzed, with some variation across countries and portfolios (Figure 4). In the 2030 *Highest impact* portfolio scenarios, required portfolio adoption levels ranged from 50% to 92% across countries (40%–87% without rebound effects). For the *General* portfolio scenario, the lowest sufficient adoption level was 54% (Hungary). With rebound re-spending, this rose to 69% in Hungary and to full adoption in Germany and Latvia. The more effective changes included in the *Highest impact* portfolio scenario reduced required average adoption levels by approximately one quarter compared to the *General* portfolio scenario.

In the 2050 scenarios, approaching the 1.5°C target would require full adoption of the *Highest impact* portfolio in all countries except Hungary, where managing rebound re-spending could lower the required adoption level to 89% (Figure 4).

Figure 2. Carbon footprints from lifestyle change portfolios and rebound emissions compared to partially decarbonized scenario carbon footprints for five EU countries in 2030 and 2050. Partially decarbonized scenario footprint includes background system changes towards 1.5°C but no household lifestyle changes. Lifestyle change portfolios include both background system changes and lifestyle changes implemented at the minimum adoption level to remain below the 1.5°C target, or at a full adoption level (100%) if the target could not be reached. For portfolios remaining within the 2030 target, the ‘without rebound emissions’ represents emissions at the adoption level necessary to offset rebound effects.

Figure 3. Average per-capita reduction in household final demand from the adoption of lifestyle change portfolios. The percent change of final demand compared to the baseline is labeled to the right of each portfolio.

3.4. Effects from rebound re-spending

When savings were distributed across the portfolio consumption structures, rebound emissions were moderate (Figure 5). Adoption of a lifestyle change portfolio partially decreased rebound potential, as emissions-intensive products and services were already partially eliminated from household consumption. Rebound emissions were higher in 2030 than in 2050 (Figure 2) despite larger absolute financial savings in 2050 in most cases (Figure 3), reflecting the lower average emissions intensity of household final demand in 2050 following background system decarbonization.

Avoiding rebound re-spending for a high-emissions alternative provided more mitigation benefit than redirecting average rebound spending to a low-emissions alternative. In 2030, directing *Highest impact* portfolio savings to *Air travel* or *Cruises/ferries* caused all countries to overshoot the 1.5°C target (Figure 5). Relative to a no-rebound scenario, re-spending on *Education* increased carbon footprints by 1-2%, and re-spending on *Recreation/culture/sports* by 2-6%, compared to 5-22% when savings were redistributed proportionally across all portfolio consumption categories at the same adoption level (Figure 5). Germany and Latvia could avoid overshooting the 1.5°C target with the *General* portfolio if savings were directed to *Education* rather than proportionally distributed.

In 2050, similar patterns emerged, but with larger cross-country variation. In Spain, average rebound re-spending under the *Highest impact* portfolio increased per-capita footprints by 0.2 tCO_{2e}, with outcomes ranging from 0.04 tCO_{2e} per capita when directed to *Education* to 2.3 tCO_{2e} per capita when directed to *Cruises/ferries*. Sweden's lower emissions intensity and smaller absolute savings limited rebound effects to a narrower range, from 0.01 to 0.18 tCO_{2e} per capita.

In all countries except Latvia, rebound emissions under the *General* portfolio scenario exceeded those of the *Highest impact* scenario (Figure 2), reflecting the more emissions-intensive consumption structure retained in the *General* portfolio. However, the *Highest impact* scenario also had the widest range of possible rebound outcomes from baseline re-spending assumptions, from 0.11 tCO_{2e} in Sweden to 0.43 tCO_{2e} in Latvia in 2030, and 0.06 tCO_{2e} to 0.37 tCO_{2e} in 2050, driven primarily by the large rebound effects observed for Latvia under the *Highest Impact* scenario, which were not present under the *General* portfolio.

3.5. Effects of applying preferences for categories of lifestyle changes

Adjusting adoption levels for citizen domain preferences did not affect whether any country could meet emissions targets in either scenario year (Figure 2). Footprints in the *General with preferences* portfolio scenario were slightly higher than those of the *General* portfolio scenario, although the financial effects were the same. This indicates that 1.5°C-compatible targets could be reached in 2030 with up to 15% lower adoption levels for mobility consumption changes than in the *General* scenario, provided that adoption levels for housing and leisure consumption changes increase by 5%.

3.6. Additional reduction of final demand to meet the 1.5°C target in 2050

As Germany, Latvia, and Sweden could not achieve 1.5°C-compatible household carbon footprints through full adoption of the *Highest impact* portfolio in 2050, additional mitigation measures in the form of further final demand reduction were modeled. The final demand reduction required to reduce carbon footprints to 1.5°C levels would be substantial (Figure S2). In this scenario, both Sweden and Germany would require a drastic reduction of final demand in addition to the measures implemented in the *Highest impact* portfolio to reach a similar level of final demand that would be compatible with a 1.5°C target. Latvia would require the most extreme reduction on an absolute level to reduce emissions to 1.5°C-compatible levels, driven by higher emissions intensities for food products than the other countries. Residual emissions remaining after *Highest impact* portfolio adoption were concentrated in diet-related categories, such as (processed) cereals, oil seeds, and vegetable oils, and the small amount of remaining animal products after lifestyle change.

Figure 4. Adoption levels compatible with the 1.5°C target for lifestyle change portfolios for five EU countries in 2030 and 2050. The 1.5°C-compatible adoption level without rebound emissions allows for the target to be met if rebound re-spending is excluded; the 1.5°C-compatible adoption level with rebound emissions includes the additional uptake of lifestyle change to offset the effects of rebound re-spending. Circles marked with “Overshoot” symbol indicate that the target is not achieved. The adoption level for the General with preferences portfolio refers to the average adoption level distributed across the entire portfolio before being adjusted for preferences. The rebound re-spending effect here refers to the average across the portfolio.

Figure 5. Carbon footprints associated with various rebound re-spending profiles for lifestyle change portfolio scenarios in 2030 and 2050. No rebound refers to the profile without accounting for emissions from re-spending any financial savings; Rebound: Average portfolio refers to the emissions associated with re-spending in the pattern of the lifestyle change portfolio; Rebound: Education refers to all financial savings being spent on 'Education services'; Rebound: Recreation/culture/sports refers to all financial savings being spent on 'Recreational, cultural and sporting services'; Rebound: Air travel refers to all financial savings being spent on 'Air transport services'; Rebound: Cruises/ferries refers to all financial savings being spent on 'Sea and coastal water transportation services'. Figures a-b present results for the General portfolio in 2030 and 2050; figures c-d present results for the Highest impact portfolio in 2030 and 2050. Countries are represented by their ISO2 codes: DE (Germany), ES (Spain), HU (Hungary), LV (Latvia), and SE (Sweden).

4. Discussion and conclusion

4.1. Modeling lifestyle change portfolios

This study identified the adoption levels at which three lifestyle change portfolios produce 1.5°C-compatible household carbon footprints in five EU countries under industrial decarbonization scenarios for 2030 and 2050. The results of this scenario analysis indicate that reducing emissions to a 1.5°C-consistent level would depend on substantial adoption of lifestyle changes against a background of rapid industrial decarbonization. These findings emphasize the need for widespread lifestyle change adoption across the EU to achieve 1.5°C-compatible household carbon footprints. The more intensive need in 2050 compared to 2030 reflects the stricter 2050 carbon budget and the slower pace of industrial decarbonization after 2030 in the SSP1-RCP1.9-aligned background scenario (Cap et al., 2024). Deviations from the SSP1-RCP1.9 decarbonization pathway would alter the remaining carbon budget compatible with 1.5°C and the stringency of household emissions targets. Results should be interpreted

as theoretical upper bounds on lifestyle change mitigation under ambitious but stylized 1.5°C-aligned decarbonization conditions, not as predictions of future behavior or likely decarbonization trajectories.

Our estimated emissions reduction potentials under industrial decarbonization and stated adoption levels align with the IPCC's 40-70% range for demand-side mitigation potential (Creutzig et al., 2022). However, our results exceed the 25-32% reported by Moran et al. (2020) due to our higher adoption level assumptions, although our reported mitigation potentials are only slightly higher than other IOA-based mitigation potentials (Guan et al., 2025; Vita et al., 2019). Our finding that Swedish decarbonization scenarios fall short of the 1.5°C target despite a decarbonized energy system is consistent with previous country-level assessments (Carlsson Kanyama et al., 2021; Morfeldt et al., 2023), and shows how a decarbonized electricity grid alone does not eliminate mitigation challenges when emissions-intensive consumption patterns persist in mobility, nutrition, and housing or overall household consumption remains high.

The modeling of detailed lifestyle change portfolios under different industrial change conditions has provided insights related to the influence of technological change not possible in previous MRIO approaches. Our approach allowed us to isolate the additional contribution of household lifestyle change measures under 1.5°C-compatible industrial decarbonization conditions. This work extends prior MRIO-based lifestyle change modeling approaches (Guan et al., 2025; Moran et al., 2020; Vita et al., 2019) to allow for prospective scenario analysis capabilities. While representation of lifestyle changes within IAMs has advanced (van Sluisveld et al., 2016; van Vuuren et al., 2018), including simulating adoption dynamics (van den Berg et al., 2024), this approach complements IAM-based scenario research with detailed lifestyle change portfolios with higher product- and country-level resolution that explicitly captures changes in emissions intensities for embodied emissions beyond energy use such as materials, food and goods production.

Key limitations of this study include the static nature of the MRIO model used, which does not represent dynamic economic or social effects of lifestyle change. Although we account for estimated household price effects from final demand changes and the adoption of new technologies, structural economic consequences and macroeconomic price responses beyond households are not assessed. And although preferences were also represented in a stylized portfolio and adoption levels modeled as a population average, tools such as agent-based models may be able to provide insights into social dynamics and heterogeneous behaviors such as preferences and acceptance alongside footprinting-based tools like MRIO-based analysis (Scherer et al., 2025).

The results presented here reflect the average transformations necessary across all households in a country for overall footprint reductions. Although carbon footprints have been decreasing over all income groups in Europe over the past decade, carbon inequality has increased as the emissions of low-income households have decreased more than those of high-income households (Chancel, 2022; Zheng et al., 2023). Based on our scenario analysis, Hungary and Spain appear to be examples of countries that can reduce 2050 footprints to 1.5°C-compatible levels. However, poverty, and particularly energy poverty, may contribute lower carbon footprints within Europe (Koukouloufikis & Uihlein, 2022). A share of the population in Hungary (~30%) and Spain (~12%) already have carbon footprints close to the 2030 target, likely due to poverty (Ivanova & Wood, 2020). Looking forward, assessing the effects of lifestyle change by income groups and heterogeneous consumption patterns under different technological and socioeconomic change scenarios would be helpful for exploring the different responsibilities for reducing consumption-based emissions.

4.2. Rebound effects and implications

Our findings about rebound effects are consistent with previous findings (e.g. Chitnis et al. (2014), Moran et al. (2020), and Vita et al. (2019)), in that the range of rebounds depends on the portfolio of consumption as well as the assumptions about re-spending. The rebounds and re-spending findings show

that it is important to divert re-spending away from high-impact categories but that the re-spending becomes less significant the more the lifestyle portfolio aligns with a low-emissions lifestyle overall.

This study considered financial rebounds, but the mechanisms of rebounds can also consider use of time (time rebounds) and other behavioral mechanisms (e.g. moral licensing). The resulting rebound depends on the resulting use of time or resulting behavior in response to the initial behavior change, with prior studies also investigating a range of high-carbon and low-carbon behaviors (Richter et al., 2024). However, studies of behavioral mechanisms also note potential for spillover effects with pro-environmental behavior changes (Maki et al., 2019). An implicit assumption in some of our portfolios is that consumption changes, particularly those made intentionally and intrinsically motivated as part of broader lifestyle goals, will constrain rebounds and can even result in positive spillover effects (i.e. low-carbon behavior changes result in additional low-carbon behavior changes) with people avoiding high-emissions activities and intentionally seeking lower-emission sectors for re-spending (this is supported in empirical studies – see Andersson & Nässén, 2023; Richter et al., 2024). Supporting intrinsic motivations through awareness campaigns and aligning behavioral choices with environmental identities can enhance positive spillovers (Maki et al., 2019; Truelove et al., 2014), which in turn may support more sufficiency-oriented policies. In addition, encouraging community-based activities can minimize rebound risks while fostering collective benefits (Richter et al., 2024; Sahakian et al., 2021).

Previous studies indicated rebounds could be addressed by implementing taxes on high-impact goods or directing savings towards low-carbon investments (e.g., education and cultural activities) (Claudelin et al., 2020; Wiedenhofer et al., 2018), the latter of which was modeled in this study. However, even more significant than directing re-spending towards low-carbon activities is directing them away from high-carbon activities, which may indicate taxing these activities is warranted. Policies should also consider the implications for fairness in how these activities are governed.

4.3. Acceptance and associated fairness, structural change, and policy implications

Implementing the levels of household and industrial decarbonization explored in this study will require deliberate policy action, including measures that reshape choice architectures, infrastructure provision, and incentive structures.

On the demand side, a transition to 1.5°C-compatible decarbonization levels will require high or even full adoption of many consumption change options. In the five countries examined in this study, switching to public transportation currently has a 62% acceptance rate on average, while switching to vegan or vegetarian diets stand at 14% and 25% (Vadovics et al., 2024). Thus, it is vital to increase the acceptance and adoption of especially the more impactful consumption change options, such as private car-based mobility and animal-based nutrition, through associated, supportive policies.

Multiple factors influence acceptance and adoption; however, acceptance does not always lead to adoption (Csutora, 2012). Perceived fairness is increasingly recognized as an important condition in the acceptance and adoption of low-carbon lifestyle changes (Hirth et al., 2023; Kreinin, Fuchs, et al., 2024; Patterson et al., 2018; Sovacool et al., 2022), and overcoming resistance to rapid decarbonization policies (Groh & Möllendorff, 2020). Evidence from citizen-focused research suggests that integrating fairness both in climate change mitigation measures and communication can strengthen public acceptance (Hobson, 2002; Howell, 2013; Schmidt-Scheele et al., 2022). Research focused on the acceptance conditions for the options studied here identified key fairness concerns raised by citizens: equitable access to affordable low-carbon products and services (e.g., public transport options, plant-based meals in schools and canteens, small-sized apartments with access to green public spaces), and support for installing low-carbon energy provisioning systems at home (Kreinin, Mamut, et al., 2024; Lehner et al., 2024; Vadovics et al., 2024).

Policies focused on implementation of lifestyle changes should consider those currently not meeting their basic needs and ensure that their situation is improved in 1.5°C-compatible ways, even in high-income EU countries (Vadovics et al., 2026). A carbon quota system could promote fairness in emissions

reduction efforts and provide an incentive for low-carbon behavior adoption, an approach several studies suggest deserves renewed policy attention (Burgess, 2016; Fuso Nerini et al., 2021; Kiss & Hajdú, 2016). Implementing a carbon tax on emissions-intensive activities and using the proceeds to fund vouchers for green household energy or public transportation in low-income households may reduce inequality, increase adoption of lifestyle change, and avoid direct rebound effects (Büchs et al., 2021).

The scenario results presented, which show the difficulties of staying within the 1.5°C limit, depend on the implementation of strict and optimistic background system changes. Without the necessary and sizeable background system changes, our analysis could underestimate the need for larger active lifestyle change, including the need for sufficiency measures (Walker Wood et al., 2024; Wiese et al., 2024). The background improvements in energy efficiency on which most 1.5°C scenarios rely may not materialize due to infrastructure and market inertia, as well as delayed or unproven technologies such as carbon capture and storage, bioenergy with carbon capture and storage, or hydrogen (Fuhrman et al., 2020; Fuss et al., 2014). The background scenario parameters derived from SSP1-RCP1.9 were not altered to incorporate potential policy implementation gaps by governments (Braunreiter et al., 2021; Wiese et al., 2024), although real-world policies for decarbonization changes necessary for 1.5°C face political resistance, economic crises, and corporate lobbying (McLaren & Markusson, 2020). Overly optimistic scenarios themselves potentially limit governmental and societal action by providing a rosy view of future mitigation possibilities and delaying strong and adequate action (McLaren & Markusson, 2020). Our analysis underlines the urgent and key role of continued and proactive governmental action to enable industrial decarbonization necessary for citizens to live lifestyles aligned with the 1.5°C limit.

While the scenario is exploratory, one reading of the results suggests a need to reconsider the goal and possibilities for economic growth in conjunction with the 1.5°C goal. If unprecedented industrial technological changes and high levels of lifestyle change adoption together are not compatible with 1.5°C decarbonization targets, other measures may be needed. This raises the question of whether economic growth itself may need to slow, halt, or even reverse in high-income countries. This is in line with recent research, including the IPCC (2022) which highlights degrowth and post-growth policies as potential avenues for staying close to the limit set in the Paris Agreement, given the strong global link between emissions and continued economic growth. Most experts consider economic growth to be the key structural barrier to achieving societies that enable citizens to live 1.5°C lifestyles (Kreinin, Fuchs, et al., 2024). Economic growth is also exacerbating inequality and wealth concentration (Kreinin et al., 2024; Keyßer & Lenzen, 2021), highlighted as a key problem for fairness and achieving the necessary policy changes that enable the structural conditions for 1.5°C lifestyles (Apeti et al., 2025). Calls for post-growth and degrowth alongside technological and demand-side solutions have been receiving increased attention in research on climate modeling (Keyßer & Lenzen, 2021), including new modified integrated assessment models that map degrowth trajectories (Li et al., 2024).

The scale of lifestyle change and industrial decarbonization required to limit warming to 1.5°C as explored in this scenario will require profound societal, economic, and technological innovations. Regardless of whether carbon footprint reductions may stimulate lower household expenditures or result from them, institutions will need to reimagine their strategies to facilitate the transition to a new societal paradigm while also avoiding both high-emissions rebound expenditures and the exacerbation of existing inequalities.

Declaration of Interest statement

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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